

Experience of Companies in Asia on Solving Plastic Waste Problem

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is an overview of plastic waste pollution, related studies, and theories related to plastic waste pollution treatment. From there, we analyze the experiences of Asian countries and draw lessons for Vietnam.

Keywords: Consumption trend of plastic products, plastic waste, Vietnam and Southeast Asia.

1. Introduction

In our country (Vietnam), plastic products began to penetrate into people's lives since the 1960s. A number of household items made from bamboo, bamboo, natural fibers ... in turn were replaced by plastic. Paper packaging has been replaced with plastic. In industry and construction, plastic materials also account for market share in many areas such as water supply and drainage, decoration etc... (Tran Hieu Nhue et al., 2001). According to Nguyen Danh Son (2012), an average Vietnamese person per year uses at least 30 kg of plastic products. Plastic materials have contributed to raising the civilized level of life but also posed many problems related to environmental protection (Tran Hieu Nhue et al., 2001). Some researches on solid waste (CTR) in urban areas in the Mekong Delta showed that the plastic composition accounted for 3.16-13.63% of the total amount of solid waste (Le Hoang Viet et al., 2011; extract from INVENT, 2009); or accounting for 77% of recyclable waste in Can Tho City (Nguyen Vo Chau Ngan et al., 2014).

In the context of economic development and changing patterns of consumption and production by people leading to a strong increase in plastic waste worldwide, the research organization on the trend of using plastic products is extremely necessary.

2. Literature review

2.1. Definition of Plastic

Plastics are a series of synthetic or semi-synthetic organic compounds that have ductility and can therefore be molded into solid objects.

Flexibility is a common property of all materials that can be irreversibly deformed without deterioration, but in materials such as molded polymers, this property reaches the level that their real name derives from the This special feature.

Plastics are typical high molecular weight organic polymers that often contain other substances. They are commonly synthesized, the most common source being petrochemical products, however, a variety of variations are made from renewable materials such as corn polylactic acid or short cotton velvet cellulose (American Chemical Council, 2011).

According to Philos, Trans, Soc (2009), about a third of plastic is used for packaging in developed economies, and in buildings such as pipes, pipes or vinyl sheets, the use of plastic is close to same. Other applications include cars (up to 20%), furniture and toys. In developing countries, the use of plastic may differ from India's 42% of consumption for packaging. Worldwide, about 50 kg of plastic is produced per person per year, and production doubles every ten years. With the advent of polymer implants and at least some other medical devices out of plastic, plastic also has many uses in the medical field. The naming in the plastic surgery field is not due to the use of plastic materials, but because of the meaning of the word "plasticity" and related to the reshaping of flesh.

The world's first synthetic resin was bakelite, invented by Leo Baekeland in New York in 1907. He coined the term "plastic" (Edgar, David, Robin, 2009). Many chemists have contributed to plastic materials science, including Nobel Prize winner Herman Staudinger, known as "the father of polymer chemistry" and Herman Mark, known as "the father of polymer physics" (Teegarden, David, 2004).

The success and dominance of plastics began in the early 20th century. Due to the composition of macromolecules, the plastic is removed as waste, and the rate of decomposition is slow, causing environmental concerns. By the end of the century, a way to solve this problem was met by a series of efforts, namely recycling.

2.2. Classification of plastic

Plastics are often classified according to the chemical structure of the main chain and the side chain of polymers; Some of the important categories in these categories are: acrylic plastics, polyester, silicone, polyurethane and halogenated plastics.

Plastics can also be classified as follows: Chemical processes used in the synthesis, such as condensation, polyaddition, and crosslinked (Wayback Machine, 2011).

Plastics can also be classified according to their various physical properties, such as hardness, density, tensile strength, resistance to heat, and glass transition temperature, and are classified by properties. their chemistry, such as the organic chemistry of polymers and their resistance and reaction to different chemical products and processes. For example: organic solvents, oxidants and radiation. In particular, most plastics melt when heated to a few hundred degrees Celsius (Kent, 2008).

Other classifications are based on quality in relation to product manufacture or design. Examples of quality and grade are: thermoplastics and thermosets, conductive polymers, biodegradable plastics, engineering plastics and other resins with special structures, such as elastomers.

An important classification of plastics is based on their permanent or impermanent morphology, whether they are thermoplastics or thermosets.

Thermoplastic is a plastic that, when heated, its composition does not change chemically, so it can be molded many times. Examples include: polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC). Conventional thermoplastics range from 20,000 to 500,000 amu, while thermosets are thought to have an infinite molecular weight.

Thermosetting polymers, or thermosetting polymers, melt and form only once: when they are solidified, they remain solid (Gilleo, Ken, 2004). During the thermosetting process, an irreversible chemical reaction occurs. Vulcanizing rubber is an example of a thermosetting process: polyisoprene is a viscous material that flows slightly before being heated with sulfur; Once vulcanization, the product is rigid and non-sticky.

Many plastics are completely amorphous, such as: all are thermosets; Polystyrene and its copolymer; and polymethyl methacrylate (Kutz, Myer, 2002).

However, some partially amorphous resins in their molecular structure, give them a melting point, temperatures that surpass intermolecular gravity and one or more glass transitions, which are higher. Significantly compared with local molecular flexibility Increased. These semi-crystalline resins include: polyethylene, polypropylene, polyvinyl chloride, polyamide (nylon), polyester and some polyurethane.

Internally conductive polymers (ICP) are conductive organic polymers. Although plastics can be made into conductive materials with a conductivity of up to 80 kS / cm in extended-oriented polyacetylene, they still cannot compare with the conductivity of most metals such as copper up to a few. hundred kS / cm. However, this is a growing field (Heeger, Schrieffer, 1988).

Biodegradable plastic refers to plastic that can degrade or decompose when exposed to sunlight or ultraviolet rays, water or moisture, bacteria, enzymes, or wind. In some cases, rodent, pest, or insect attacks can also be viewed as a form of biodegradation or environmental degradation.

Some degradation modes require plastic to be in contact with a surface (aerobic), while others are only effective (anaerobic) if there are certain conditions in the composting or burial system.

Some companies produce biodegradable additives to enhance biodegradation. Plastic can be added to the starch as a filler to make it more susceptible to degradation, but this still does not result in complete decomposition of the plastic.

Some researchers have used genetically modified bacteria to synthesize completely biodegradable plastics, such as Biopol; However, these prices are currently very high. (Brandl.Helmut, Puchner, Pentra, 1992)

Although most plastics are manufactured from petrochemical products, biology is essentially made from renewable plant materials like cellulose and starch. The development of bioplastics is a growing field due to limited petrochemical reserves and the threat of global warming.

However, the basis for the development of bioplastics is very low, and so far it is not very large compared to petrochemical production. The production capacity of global biological derivatives is estimated at 327,000 tons / year. In contrast, polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) are the world's leading petrochemical- derived polyolefins, with global production estimated to exceed 150 million tonnes in 2015 (Galie, Fabrizio, 2016).

2.3. Plastic applications and its social benefits

Around 1600 BC, ancient Central Americans processed natural rubber into balls, statues, and ice for the first time (Hosler et al., 1999), and since then humans have benefited from the use of polymers. During this period, people became increasingly dependent on plastics and rubber, first experimenting with natural polymers, horns, wax, natural rubber and plastic until the 19th century, modern thermoplastics began develop.

In 1839, Goodyear invented vulcanized rubber, and German pharmacist Edward Simon discovered polystyrene (PS). During the 19th century, development of natural / synthetic polymers was underway, producing famous products such as celluloid for billiards, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for a variety of purposes and viscose (rayon) for clothes. Products. The development of modern plastics really expanded in the first 50 years of the 20th century, with at least 15 new polymers being synthesized. Plastic has enjoyed great success as a material; They have been shown to be widely used in a wide range of types and forms, including natural polymers, modified natural polymers, thermosets, thermoplastics, and near biodegradable resins. here. Plastics have a variety of unique properties: they can be used in a wide temperature range, chemical and light resistant, they are very strong and tough, but can be easily processed like hot run. This series of properties and low cost drives the annual worldwide demand for plastics to reach 245 million tonnes (Platics Europe, 2008).

2.4. Plastic waste

Like all consumable materials, the treatment of plastic materials can lead to an increase in municipal waste and the generation of additional municipal waste. Urban waste is increasing, including a large amount of waste, including thermoplastic products. Thermoplastics are not biodegradable in the environment and plastic waste can persist for a long time (Andrady, 2003). The exact life of waste plastic depends on the chemical properties of the material, and the properties of its environment depend on how "degradation" is determined or measured, and therefore varies greatly. Degradation can be degraded by biodegradation or environmental degradation (wind, rain, sunlight); For compost resins, this can happen within a few months, but for traditional plastics, it takes a long time (Andrady, 2003). Comparing plastic to other waste materials like lignocellulosic paper, which is particularly durable in the environment due to its chemical properties, and this toughness makes it difficult to find a source of plastic waste. However, litter is a behavioral issue that needs to be addressed primarily through

education. More attention and resources is needed to raise consumer awareness of the environmental consequences of waste, as this is the most effective solution. In Singapore, for example, a government scheme to impose huge fines and repair work orders has proven to be a very effective anti-litter measure.

A phenomenon of particular concern is the amount of plastic waste entering the world's oceans, mainly from terrestrial sources (Thompson et al., 2005; the most recent reviews suggest Barnes et al. (2009), Gregory (2009); Ryan et al (2009); According to a report by Green Peace Allsopp et al., the authors estimate that waste is 0.2-0.3%. (2006) Plastic debris in the World's Oceans (2006) and world plastic

production figures (Plastics Europe, 2006) for the past 10 years came from tourists, sewage spills, yards near-shore landfills, illegal and industrial leaks. The durability of plastics promotes their use in a wide range of applications (as discussed earlier), and when this material eventually becomes garbage waste, it can also lead to ecological problems. As the gears are mainly made of plastic, the fish box and other accessories are also made of plastic, it is not surprising that the wreckage is involved. to fishing will eventually flow into the world's oceans.

According to Waste Management Series (2004), plastic waste is ground, washed and stirred giving it an aqueous suspension, which is separated by three consecutive centrifuges. Plastic pollution is the accumulation of plastic products in the environment including soil and oceans, adversely affecting wildlife, wildlife habitats and humans. Plastic waste includes disposable plastic products such as plastic bags, plastic bottles, plastic straws, and other plastic products.

There are many ways to classify plastic waste such as relying on polluting plastic waste including soil and oceans. Plastic waste can also be sorted by recyclable and non-recyclable. In addition, plastic waste can be sorted based on the source generated such as from households, from manufacturing enterprises or from public places. The most common classifications may be based on the different resins we use including:

PET or Polyethylene terephthalate

This plastic beverage and perishable beverage packaging is plastic and is said to be a safe and recyclable plastic by shredding and then reusing into other products such as bottles, rugs or furniture and garments.

HDPE or High-Density Polyethylene

This is another type of plastic that can be classified as safe. We can find this plastic in baby shower bottles and baby toys. HDPE does not lose shape or deteriorate under sunlight, so it is used for outdoor furniture and trash.

PVC or Polyvinyl Chloride

It is a form of plastic that can be used for pipes, windows and various types of medical devices and is used in applications that require plastic to bend, including plastic wrap and cables. This type of plastic, called toxic plastic, should not be used for food or drinks because it contains toxic chemicals. There is a link between these chemicals and liver disease and developmental problems in children.

LDPE or low-density polyethylene

This safe and clean plastic is popular in a number of items including plastic shopping bags and squeezable bottles. After recycling, we can reuse it in items like bubble wrap and even furniture.

PP or Polypropylene

This type of plastic is known for its durability and safety for use in items such as Tupperware plastic containers and even medicine bottles.

PS or Polystyrene

Polystyrene is a familiar plastic used to protect around packaged items, it is also used as insulation and in cups. Because this is a weak plastic, it is very fragile and spreads easily through the environment, making it very difficult to recycle.

Other plastic

Other types of items that can be difficult to recycle include sunglasses, bottles and even CDs. They contain BPA, a toxic chemical and can cause hormonal disruptions as well as a range of health problems.

2.5. Overview of previous studies related to the topic

In her doctoral dissertation, Thu (2018) explores the factors that influence customers' purchasing green products. The thesis studies customers' intention to buy green products, especially related to food products with environmentally friendly packaging. Our research focuses on packaged foods, especially packaged instant noodles, in the developing market. The author said that it would be useful to focus on understanding the special relationship between the intention to buy the product and the willingness of customers to open their bags to buy environmentally friendly packaging. Thu (2018) believes that people are more likely to buy green products if they consider themselves an environmentalist or an activist in environmental issues.

Mui (2018) surveyed the current status of plastic waste and proposed limited solutions in Can Tho in her research.

Loan (2013) researches the topic "Management of domestic solid waste in Quoc Oai district, Hanoi city" to limit the level of environmental pollution caused by waste and reduce the cost of domestic solid waste management. . Accordingly, the majority of domestic waste in this locality is plastic waste and has not yet been treated. The author proposes measures to improve waste pollution, including increasing resources and budget for waste management in general and plastic waste in particular. At the same time, the ministries from the city to the commune need to develop specific action plans according to the goals set by the state and the city government.

Thuy .et el (2015) delves into Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), one of the most popular materials that is widely used in many fields with a very fast growth rate. Research shows that the level of PET plastic consumption is increasing. The annual amount of PET waste discharged into the environment is very large. Thuy et el. (2015) explored PET recycling methods as well as the possibilities and scope of the recycled PET application and proposed the application of recycling technology or reuse of waste PET plastic to contribute to prevent prevent environmental pollution, and limit the ability to exploit resources.

The rapid urbanization and economic growth in different countries have led to a drastic increase in plastic production and consumption around the globe. Owing to the low recycling value of plastic and the lack of technological support, the recovery rate of plastic waste remains very low. Most of it is washed into the ocean, disposed of in landfills, or burned in incinerators. These enormous amounts of plastic waste bring disastrous consequences, such as pollution, food chain con-tamination, biodiversity breakdowns, energy waste, and economic loss.

There have been a lot of studies on plastic waste, the serious problems that plastic waste causes to the living environment and solutions to solve the above problem. Chow (2017) studied Plastic Waste Problem and Education for Plastic Waste Management. This research points to a dramatic increase in worldwide plastic waste and the disposal of plastic waste that is harmful to the environment and threatening human health. Chow (2017) emphasizes that in order to reduce plastic

waste, education is extremely important because education can change people: Knowledge, attitude and behavior towards plastic waste management. Fobil (2006) studies plastic wastes in a developing economy and offers an approach for Ghana. Accordingly, this study shows that the packaging revolution in Ghana has not

been adequately supported by the appropriate plastic waste management policy, causing cities to be flooded with plastic waste; thus, creating visual disturbances and other public health problems. The paper discusses the experiences, challenges and prospects of plastic waste management programs in Ghana and proposes a new tax model that addresses this environmental problem. The author promotes a long-term remedy such as a polluted tax system that is handled carefully.

Research by Purwoko (2016) suggests that the current development of plastic technology has found that environmentally friendly plastics, in particular, biodegradable plastics can decompose in a shorter period of time. Technological improvements are still ongoing, but biodegradable plastics are more expensive than non-biodegradable plastics. People tend to choose inexpensive, non-biodegradable plastics and avoid expensive biodegradable plastics. Purwoko's study (2016) provides a fiscal policy alternative to reduce the amount of plastic waste. This study concludes that a combination of incentive and disrespectful fiscal policies can be applied to reduce the amount of plastic waste. Financial incentives (subsidies) may be applied to increase the use of biodegradable plastics and policies that are not financially appropriate can be applied to reduce the use of non-biodegradable plastics without causing burden for the government.

In Vietnam, there was a study by Linh et al. (2019) on factors affecting consumer behavior. This study analyzed factors affecting consumers, behavioral intent to reduce plastic waste. The results have been confirmed that an attitude of acceptance of a change in an individual's ability to reduce plastic waste. Based on these findings, the author has made a number of recommendations that have been proposed to enhance individual consumer behavioral intent to reduce plastic waste.

These plastic waste problems and adverse effects are especially serious and omnipresent in renowned countries/mega cities such as Japan (PWMI,2014), Taiwan

(Walther,2015), the UK (GHK,2006; Howarth,2013), and Hong Kong (Environmental Protection Department,2013), where economic activities are flourishing and the plastic consumption level is high. Plastic waste not only causes air pollution (Li, Lee, Mi, & Su,1995), land pollution (Barnes, Galgani, Thompson, Barlaz,2009;Steelys Drinkware,2013), and harms human health (Crinnion,2010; Elliott et al.,1996; Maffini, Rubin, Sonnenschein, & Soto,2006; Yamamoto & Yasuhara,1999),but it also causes water pollution (Howarth,2013; Laist,1987; Perkins,2014;Schwartz,2014; Zielinski,2014) and contaminates the food chain (Rochman et al.,2014; Swan,2008; Thompson, Moore, Saal, & Swan,2009), endangers biodiversity (Derraik, 002; Grant & Ryder, 2009; Gregory, 2009. McNamee,2008), and causes enormous energy waste (Cho,2012; European Commission,2013; HongKong Cleanup,2012; StudyMode,2015; Themelis & Mussche,2014).

In general, studies have addressed the problem of plastic waste in many countries around the world and Asia, many solutions have been implemented and many experiences have been drawn. However, a full study of solutions that countries and businesses have applied and specific lessons for Vietnam to reduce the problem of plastic waste has not been fully studied, especially one overall solution for plastic waste reduction planning and effective implementation of recycling industry.

3. Plastic waste problem

Plastics are a petrochemical-based synthetic material used as a raw material in a range of industries including textiles, packaging, household appliances, electricity and water, as well as automotive and aircraft manufacturing. With only one-third of plastic materials recovered for recycling or reuse, most of them have been dumped into the sea and oceans causing serious problems. Most marine debris is plastic and it takes more than 400 years for them to decompose or biodegrade to harm over 200 different marine species and human health. Many animals have accidentally ingested plastic debris, resulting in suffocation, malnutrition and even death. Originally manufactured products found in textiles or cosmetics and personal care products, etc., are difficult to find and recover because they are the result of larger pieces of plastic being broken into smaller

pieces. Plastic debris often contains toxic chemicals including unburnt compounds that cause tens of billions of dollars in annual damage to coastal cleanup, fisheries, maritime transport and tourism (UNEP, 2014).

With 242 million tons of plastic waste generated by the world in 2016 (World Bank 2018), the World Bank believes that the accumulation of plastic waste in recent decades has actually had a negative impact on the surrounding environment and human health. In addition to taking hundreds to thousands of years to disintegrate in nature, plastic waste can cause floods due to sewage clogging, shortening the life span of animals when consumed, causing respiratory illness when burning, and polluting the bodies of water when they fall into canals and oceans. By 2050, there will be more plastic in the ocean than fish (by weight) if there is no effective solution. When plastic waste is poorly managed by a country / business, they enter the environment through dumping, landfill and disposal by water. According to statistics, more than 25% of plastic waste is dumped openly and plastic waste is also increasing due to improperly managed official disposal sites. Even when garbage is collected collectively, many countries lack waste treatment capabilities and technologies. Many developed countries have policies to export plastic waste to less developed countries such as Europe exported 1/6 of the quality of plastic waste to Asia in 2017 (World Bank, 2018).

Plastic waste has become a major global concern. Plastic production and consumption worldwide have increased by 10% per year from 5 million tons in 1950 to 245 million tons in 2006. A study by Howarth (2013) suggests that consumers are still not easily to recycle their plastic waste. It is also unclear for many types of plastic accepted for recycling. Some of these plastics must be taken to recycling centers, but PVC is completely non-recyclable.

There is also a large amount of plastic that is ultimately not recycled or sent to landfills, but ultimately pollutes the natural environment. For example, in the Pacific, due to the current, a large amount of plastic and other waste materials have formed gradually, not even easily seen because the plastic has decomposed into small and attractive polymers. Chlorinated dioxins are eaten by marine organisms. Accordingly, these substances can penetrate the human food chain and cause serious health problems (Howarth, 2013). Michael (2015) also argues that plastic waste escaping disposal in a recycling, incineration or landfill facility is likely to reach oceans. Most of the dominant plastics, such as polyethylene and polypropylene, float to the ocean. Michael (2015) also argues that the results of studies so far show that different types of plastic materials differ in their tendency to carry pollutants. The most widely used polymer: polyethylene is particularly susceptible to organic molecules from seawater and acts as carriers to feed them into the food web, although theoretically, the particles are buried in sediment thus can remove pollutants from circulation. Therefore, the problem of plastic waste affects not only the environment but also human health. So, many companies are trying to replace oil-based chemicals currently used in production with a lignin-derived chemical. Lignin is a complex hydrocarbon found in the cell walls of plants and is widely available because it is a waste product from the pulp and paper industry. This research makes plastics not only more environmentally friendly, but also reduces production costs (Howarth, 2013).

Steelys (2013) in the study referred to the global landfill crisis, which is mainly caused by plastic waste. The environmental issues caused by landfills are numerous with the scope of our global garbage crisis that may exceed the challenges we are currently facing. Billions of tons of waste sent to landfills are creating serious problems for future generations with most of this landfill being plastic or polystyrene oil. These substances are used to produce bottles, mugs and containers, contain toxins and decompose at a very slow rate (1,000 years or more) and contain many toxins. Research shows that plastic containers account for nearly 50% of recyclable landfill waste and currently only recycle about 27% of plastic bottles and the rest mostly goes to landfills or is discharged into the environment.

In a recent simulation, Marcus Eriksen from the Five Gyres Institute in Los Angeles, USA estimated that there are 5.25 trillion plastic items weighing more than 268,000 tons floating in the ocean. Researchers have put these data sets into computer models and the specific results of this model research have surprised and motivated further research. Although the sources of plastic waste are thought to, including densely populated lands and

transport routes, are more concentrated in the north than in the southern hemisphere, data show that plastic accumulates in the north and south hemisphere are the same. The authors speculate that removal mechanisms, such as leaching on beaches, help limit the density of floating plastic debris in the north. However, the comprehensive model of global plastic distribution in the oceans still has many unanswered questions, especially about the interaction of plastics with living organisms (Michael, 2015).

The development of biodegradable plastics or microorganisms suitable for plastic decomposition will be the best strategy for plastic waste. In Manoj et al (2016), six different types of starch resins (low density polyethylene [LDPE], 10%, 20% 30%, 40% and 50% LDPE starch) to be evaluated price of biodegradation of various types of encapsulated resins in soil environments containing microbial collections to enhance biodegradation. Accordingly, soil degradation increases with increasing starch content in LDPE and the best results are obtained in starch containing samples by more than 30%. At the same time degradation in soil is better than compost. Thus, with an appropriate environment, plastic materials have better decomposition capacity and contribute to solving the problem of plastic waste (Michael, 2015).

4. Theoretical framework

4.1. Homans's theory of rational choice

George Homans (1910–1989) was an American sociologist, one of the famous authors of the theory of social exchange. G. Homans was elected President of American Sociology in 1964 and was appointed professor emeritus at Harvard University in 1988.

When studying social behavior, G. Homans introduced the concept of "elementary social behavior" which is understood as behaviors that people repeat regardless of whether it was planned in advance. is not. Elementary social behavior is played out in many forms, from conditional reflexes to skills, techniques to habits. According to G. Homans, elementary behavior is the basis of communication between two or more people.

G. Homans points out three basic characteristics of social behavior. First, realization - behavior must be performed in reality, not in concept. Second, the behavior is rewarded or punished by others. Third, the other person here must be the direct reinforcement of the behavior rather than the mediating figure of a certain social structure ([1]13).

When studying behavior, Homans came up with six propositions of rational behavior, including: (1) the reward proposition (the more likely it is that the act that is rewarded is more likely to be repeated); (2) the stimulus proposition (if a stimulus has ever caused an action to be rewarded, the more likely a new stimulus is to resemble that stimulus, the more likely it is to make the action the same as before. repeat as much); (3) the value proposition (the higher the value of the action, the more likely the subject is to repeat the action); (4) the rational proposition (individuals will choose the actions for which the greatest value or ability to achieve results); (5) the proposition of diminishing value (the value of the reward will decrease with regular receipt of the reward); and (6) the expectation proposition (actors will be satisfied if their expectations are fulfilled and vice versa).

Rational choice theory is based on the assumption that people always act purposefully to maximize benefits. When doing something, people also think to choose the plan to use the resources to achieve maximum results with the lowest cost. The term "choice" is used to emphasize consideration and calculation to decide which optimal means to use that achieve high results in a scarce resource condition. Applying this theory to the research topic to explain why the trend of consuming plastic products continues to increase even though it exists a hazard to the environment, with awareness of environmental problems in the current time whether they can achieve maximum efficiency in life or not, it is necessary to find that the choice is only reasonable on the basis of evaluating the objective factors and conditions of the action from the subject's side, from the subjective perspective of the decision maker, it is difficult to rely on accurate calculations. In addition, the view of rational

choice will be integrated analysis and application in making solutions to a sustainable environmental development strategy.

Moreover, individuals are also the subject of socio-economic activities based on a rational choice - a broad approach to understanding the consumption trends of plastic products. The selection of different modes of socio-economic activities is based on a balance between costs and benefits, appropriate to the livelihoods they have, their living context and choice of bearing. economic efficiency is high, income is stable and life is stable or not. This is a theory suitable for the types of behaviors that people often choose in daily life for research topic.

4.2. Theory of cultural ecology

The concept of ecology was initiated by the German naturalist Haeckel in 1866, Cultural ecology is a theory that investigates the reciprocal relationship between humans and the surrounding natural environment, as well as understands culture as the product of that relationship. Cultural ecology asserts that the culture of each ethnic group is created due to the resources and limitations of the surrounding environment, including changes in that environment. Here, the concept of "culture type" plays a fundamental role, it is understood as a set of distinctive features for a resulting lifestyle adapting to the surrounding environment and forming the nucleus of culture - what is associated with activities that create means of existence, economic institutions, politics, society, religion, etc. In other words, the approach to ecology of 25 cultures requires deep understanding of the content, characteristics and socio- spiritual consequences of a certain culture in the natural environment that forms them. From there, we learn about issues of natural ecosystems, rural ecosystems and urban ecosystems, which are open ecosystems with different economic, cultural - social perspectives. These ecological models need to take in energy and raw materials, and output many materials, products and also energy from the environment and human activity creating imbalances of factors. This nature, further promoting the change of the living environment in a direction that is detrimental to humans, makes the living environment face formidable challenges.

However, the theory of cultural ecology also has certain limitations, it is easy to see that many times the same natural environment gives rise to different cultures. For example, living under the same conditions of land, climate, and water resources,

but while there are communities that exploit knowledge and experience to both generate high productivity and conserve resources, find out new technological measures, create high-productivity ecosystems, many measures to increase human health and longevity, there are also groups of people who perceive natural resources as endlessly, they have exploited this source of wealth indiscriminately to then lead everyone into a common environmental tragedy. This is not to mention that culture and nature always interact with each other, one world shapes the other, but the theory of cultural ecology has not clarified the adverse effects of culture on the environment nature. Therefore, the application of the theory to this research topic to analyze the plastic waste problem stems from the tendency of people to consume plastic products and the change of living environment, to raise awareness in limiting use of plastic products by people.

5. Experience of companies in Asia on solving plastic waste problem

5.1. Issue internal environment policies

In McDonald's, with more than 36,000 restaurants in 122 locations, this company has also made a landmark decision to ensure 100% of its packaging comes from renewable, recyclable sources. Evian, a world-famous brand of bottled water, is also on the front line of the battle to reduce plastic waste with the introduction of a new carbon-free bottling plant and by 2025, the French company is committed to producing only 100% recycled bottles (Adam, 2018).

In China, private companies, as well as small businesses and local shops, play an important role in reducing plastic pollution. Businesses are actively eliminating the use of non-biodegradable plastic bags, supporting research, investing in replacing non-plastic products and technologies to help improve the recycling efficiency of plastic waste. Tianyuan Corporation and Jiuhe Tiaoma, for example, have increased their investments in biodegradable plastic bags and recycling lines.

Chinese e-commerce giants, including Alibaba, Suning and Jingdong, have used various incentives such as discounts and shopping vouchers. These promotions have encouraged consumers to choose green packaging in online orders, such as ice-free boxes and biodegradable packaging materials. In 2017, Alibaba introduced the Green Logistics Plan 2020 with the purpose of using eco-friendly packaging bags and exclusive recycling boxes. In 2017, Meituan, one of China's largest online food ordering companies, started the 'Green Mountain Cooperation Initiative' to address environmental issues related to the real-world delivery industry. This initiative has helped different stakeholders work together to reduce packaging waste from sources, improve recycling and promote environmental protection at the same time. Meituan works with universities to conduct research on how to improve environmental sustainability and evaluate the company's delivery impact on the environment. In general, private companies in China have gradually realized the prestigious benefits of a positive social image and the direction to reduce plastic pollution is a clear sign.

In Indonesia, large multinational companies also contributed many effective solutions to solve the plastic waste problem of Indonesia. Nestlé Indonesia introduced optimized plastic wrap and empowered local factories to manage waste by environmentally friendly vehicles. Nestlé has also promoted hundreds of thousands of Nestlé suppliers (Indonesian farmers), to minimize plastic waste. In addition, Nestlé has built an alliance with five other companies to create PRAISE (Packaging and Recycling Alliance for Indonesia Sustainable Environment) to support an integrated, friendly waste management system. In addition, Borealis AG, a global plastic manufacturer, has donated most of the funding for the STOP Ocean Plastic project in 2017 and selected Banyuwangi in Indonesia as the first beneficiary city in this project to reduce and eliminate plastic leaks into the environment.

5.2. Classified waste and develop recyclable products

Indonesia's Plastics and Plastics Industry Association (Inaplas) has pledged \$ 1 billion to reduce plastic waste (including a \$ 100 million loan from the World Bank). Through redesigning product packaging, using recyclable materials and adequate waste management, Indonesia aims to reduce the amount of plastic it leaks into the ocean by 70%. Although the country has invested in a large-scale recycling industry, with about 1.1 million tons / year of plastic waste being recycled, the recycling rate remains low at 20% (Messe, 2019).

At An Phat Plastic Company (AAA), the main raw material in the production of PE resins - products from non-renewable resources. Therefore, AAA has invested in a recycling line system, utilizing raw materials consumed in the manufacturing process. In addition, promoting environmentally-friendly products also helps to limit the use of PE resins, as compound compound produces biodegradable microbial products completely derived from corn starch and does not cause environmental pollution. AAA also strives to apply production initiatives to minimize the proportion of scrap in production, and has also invested in a recycling system that saves raw materials with a scrap rate of only 5.2% (Annual report of AAA, 2018).

At Binh Minh Plastic Company (BMP), only a very small part of waste is generated in the production process and this company does not have to use recycled materials. On the other hand, all of Binh Minh's plastic products have completely a new additive system that does not contain heavy metals, ensuring user health and environmentally friendly (Annual report of BMP, 2018).

Toray Group, a major plastic company in Asia, has implemented zero emission initiatives to realize a world based on sustainable recycling. According to the Environmental Plan, the Group has made every effort to

achieve very high targets for simply disposed waste (1), landfill waste (2) and recycled waste (3), which have been set as indicators for measuring progress toward attaining zero emissions. In which:

- (1) Simply disposed waste rate = (incineration + landfill) / total waste
- (2) Landfill waste rate = landfill waste / total waste
- (3) Recycling rate = (recycled resources + resources with monetary worth)

/(total waste + resources with monetary worth) (Annual report of Toray, 2018).

LG Chem's Cheongju plant shifted from incineration and landfill to recycling as construction cover material. In 2018, by recycling synthetic plastic waste into plastic materials, Cheongju Plant reduced about 1,769 tons of waste. LG Chem's Ochang plant has also turned raw materials to polarize packaging materials from wood to recyclable paper, reducing packaging waste by about 74 tons (Annual report of LG Chem, 2018).

At Astral Pipes, all products manufactured by the company are 100% recyclable and waste during production can be easily processed and then mixed with raw materials. Therefore, most of the waste is reused and recycled (Annual report of Astral Pipes, 2018).

At Nestle, the company aims to have no packaging, not even plastic, taken to landfills, in oceans, lakes and rivers. Accordingly, 100% of Nestle's packaging aims to be recyclable or reusable by 2025. Nestle is determined to reduce the use of disposable plastic by introducing reusable packaging everywhere operate and sell

products. In early 2020, Nestle announced an investment of up to CHF 2 billion to change from virgin plastic to recycled plastic in the food supply process and promote the development of environmentally friendly packaging solutions. Nestle will also continue to develop programs for collecting, sorting and recycling plastic waste throughout the countries where it operates. At the same time, Nestle is committed to training consumers by labeling their product packaging with recycling information - to help users identify and ensure proper disposal (Nestle, 2020).

5.3. Taking advantage of plastic waste to produce other materials

Many manufacturers have also used software that allows wasteful considerations during product design and material selection with the least environmental impact. Many processes using waste materials have been developed by companies as inputs for other products, such as new garments made from plastic and textiles. As a market for used goods is developed, the demand for new products will decrease (Sustainable Brand, 2017).

5.4. Use alternative materials

Adidas has announced plans to eliminate the use of virgin plastic from its products by 2024. Adidas has also partnered with Parley through footwear, clothing made with recycled ocean plastic, the company have produced 11 million pairs of shoes containing recycled ocean plastic. Each component of the Adidas shoe is made of 100% reusable Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) and instead of throwing away the shoe, the customer can send it back to Adidas. Then, at Adidas, the materials are recycled for the next iteration, with no waste and nothing thrown away.

Coca-Cola Company, meanwhile, introduced Dasani water in aluminum cans and bottles in the fall in the Northeast and expanded to other areas by 2020. The company also announced it would introduce a new plastic bottle using use recycled plastic by 50% to reduce the amount of virgin plastic it is using in an effort to continuously reduce its environmental footprint through smarter packaging design and procurement of recycled materials. Similarly, PepsiCo also announced plans to introduce Aquafina in aluminum cans to eliminate 8,000 tons of virgin plastic waste in a greater public goal of not using anything other than recyclable packaging and

can be biodegradable or biodegradable. Starbucks Group is also working to reduce plastic waste by announcing that it will eliminate single-use plastic straws from more than 28,000 of its operated stores by offering lids without straws or material straw with replacement materials (Brett, 2019).

In Indonesia, small and large companies in the private sector have solved the plastic waste problem in many different ways. For example, Evoware invented a seaweed-based packaging technology that is 100% biodegradable, can dissolve in warm water and has a shelf life of two years without preservatives. This initiative reduces the supply of seaweed in the country and creates business opportunities for seaweed growers. Avani is a private company based in Bali that promotes plastic pollution prevention technologies and solutions. The bags provided by Avani are biodegradable and made from vegetable cassava. Eco Bali also in Bali, provides waste management (at a small cost) and recycling to households, businesses and school waste collection infrastructure (Beatriz, 2019).

REFERENCES

- i. Adam. W. (2018). 5 companies leading the movement to go plastic free. Available at: <http://www.climateaction.org/news/5-companies-leading-the-movement-to-go-plastic-free>
- ii. Beatriz G., Mandy M. F. and Jolene L. (2019). Marine Plastic Pollution in Asia: All Hands on Deck! *Chinese Journal of Environmental Law*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1163/24686042-12340034>. Available at: https://brill.com/view/journals/cjel/3/1/article-p11_2.xml?language=en. Viewed on 15 Apr 2020.
- iii. Bliss Saigon. (2016). Vietnam and plastic pollution. Available at: <http://blissisaigon.com/vietnam-starts-to-fight-back-on-plastic-pollution/>. Viewed on 01 Mar 2020.
- iv. Brett.H. (2019). 5 Companies Taking Big Steps To Reduce Virgin Plastic Waste. Available at: <https://www.benzinga.com/news/19/09/14336655/5-companies-taking-big-steps-to-reduce-virgin-plastic-waste>. Viewd on 03 Mar 2020.
- v. Chow CF., So WM.W., Cheung TY., Yeung SK.D. (2017) Plastic Waste Problem and Education for Plastic Waste Management. In: Kong S., Wong T., Yang M., Chow C., Tse K. (eds) *Emerging Practices in Scholarship of Learning and Teaching in a Digital Era*. Springer, Singapore
- vi. Chow, Cheuk-Fai & So, Winnie & Cheung, Yannes Tsz-Yan & Yeung, Siu Kit. (2017). Plastic Waste Problem and Education for Plastic Waste Management. 10.1007/978-981-10-3344-5_8.
- vii. Choudhury Rudra Charan Mohanty, Amit Jain (2019). Plastic waste and marine plastic pollution in South Asia. Available at: https://www.ccet.jp/sites/default/files/inline-files/2-1_UNCRD_Plastic%20Waste%20%20Marine%20Plastic%20Pollution%20in%20SA-Mohanty-FINAL.pdf. Viewed on 15 Apr 2020.
- viii. Danny M. (2019). Southeast Asia's plastic waste problem. Available at: <https://www.eastasiaforum.org/2019/06/26/southeast-asias-plastic-waste-problem/>. Viewed on 13 Mar 2020.
- ix. Dezan S. (2015). Breaking the Mold: FDI Opportunities in ASEAN's Plastics Industry. Available at: <https://www.aseanbriefing.com/news/breaking-the-mold-fdi-opportunities-in-aseans-plastics-industry>. Viewed on 16 Apr 2020
- x. Dominic F. (2018). Asian plastic is choking the world's oceans. Available at: <https://asia.nikkei.com/Spotlight/Cover-Story/Asian-plastic-is-choking-the-world-s-oceans>. Viewed on 10 Mar 2020.
- xi. Engoo. (2017). Asia's Booming Plastics Industry Prompts Ocean Pollution Fears. Available at: <https://engoo.com.vn/app/daily-news/article/asias-booming-plastics-industry-prompts-ocean-pollution-fears/tMX7jlfdeenzS-B9ii6vw>. Viewed on 9 Mar 2020.
- xii. Ewa R. (2019). *Compostable Polymer Materials (Second Edition)*
- xiii. Fobil. (2006). The dilemmas of plastic wastes in a developing economy: Proposals for a sustainable management approach for Ghana. Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/wajae/article/view/45716>. Viewed on 12 Mar 2020.

- xiv. Gaelle. G. (2015). *Global Plastic Production Rises, Recycling Lags*. Available at: <http://www.plastic-resource-center.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Global-Plastic-Production-RisesRecycling-Lags.pdf>. Viewed on 13 Mar 2020.
- xv. Hiệp hội nhựa Việt Nam. (2016). *Tổng quan ngành nhựa Việt nam*. Available at: <http://vpas.vn/gioithieu/tong-quan-nganh.html>. Viewed on 9 Mar 2020.
- xvi. Howarth, S. (2013). *Why plastic waste is such a problem and the future of bioplastics*. Huffpost Tech. Retrieved from http://www.huffingtonpost.co.uk/simon-howarth/why-plastic-waste-is-such-a-problem_b_3346167.html.
- xvii. Jenna R. Jambeck, Roland Geyer, Chris Wilcox, Theodore R. Siegler, Miriam Perryman, Anthony Andrady, Ramani Narayan, Kara Lavender Law. (2015) .*Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean*. *Science* 13 Feb 2015 : 768-771
- xviii. Kang, J. (2019). *Challenges to Solving the Problem of Plastic Waste*. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6(12) 94-102.
- xix. Kaza, Silpa, Lisa Yao, Perinaz Bhada-Tata, and FrankVan Woerden. 2018. *What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050*. Urban Development Series. Washington, DC: World Bank. doi:10.1596/978-1-4648-1329-0. License: Creative Commons Attribution CC BY 3.0 IGO
- xx. Loan (2013). *Quản lý chất thải rắn sinh hoạt huyện Quốc Oai, thành phố Hà Nội*. Available at: [http://www.hus.vnu.edu.vn/files/ChuaPhanLoai/LuanVanThacSi-ChuaPhanLoai%20\(246\).pdf](http://www.hus.vnu.edu.vn/files/ChuaPhanLoai/LuanVanThacSi-ChuaPhanLoai%20(246).pdf). Viewed on 15 Apr 2020.
- xxi. Manoj .K, Sabike .N, Mythri .S .(2016). *Studies on Biodegradation of Plastic Packaging Materials in Soil Bioreactor*. Manoj Kumar1*, Sabike Noobia2, S. Mythri. Available at : <https://www.ijacskros.com/artcles/IJACS-2S-62.pdf>
- xxii. Meidl, Rachel A. (2018). *Plastic Waste Management: Are We on the Right Path to Sustainability?* Issue brief no. 11.20.18 Rice University's Baker Institute for Public Policy, Houston, Texas.
- xxiii. Messe D. (2019). *Southeast Asia: a wild card in the global plastics industry*. Available at: https://www.k-globalgate.com/en/Press/Press_Releases/Southeast_Asia_a_wild_card_in_the_global_plastics_industry. Viewed on 10 Apr 2020
- xxiv. Michael .G, (2015). *Oceans of plastic waste*, *Current Biology*, Volume 25, Issue 3, 2015, Pages R93-R96, ISSN 0960- 9822, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2015.01.038>.
- xxv. Michel B. (2013). *Thermoplastics and Thermoplastic Composites (Second Edition)*
- xxvi. Muharram A. R. (2019). *Indonesia's Battle Against Plastic Pollution*. Available at: <https://th.boell.org/en/2019/10/28/indonesias-battle-against-plastic-pollution>. Viewed on 10 Mar 2020.
- xxvii. Nestle. (2020). *What is Nestlé doing to tackle plastic packaging waste?*. Available on: <https://www.nestle.com/ask-nestle/environment/answers/tackling-packaging-waste-plastic-bottles>. Viewed on 06 Mar 2020.
- xxviii. Nhan dan. (2019). *Tìm ra quy trình tái chế hoàn toàn rác thải nhựa thành nhựa chất lượng cao*. Available at : <https://congnghiepmoitruong.vn/tim-ra-quy-trinh-tai-che-hoan-toan-rac-thai-nhua-thanh-nhua-chat-luong-cao-3705.html>
- xxix. Pat. D. (2020). *In Asia, sustainability leadership in the 2020s must start with rethinking waste*. Available at: <http://www.ethicalcorp.com/asia-sustainability-leadership-2020s-must-start-rethinking-waste>. Viewed on 13 Mar 2020.
- xxx. Purwoko. (2016). *Fiscal Incentives And Disincentives To Reduce Plastic Waste In Indonesia*. Available at: <http://aasic.org/proc/aasic/article/view/360>. Viewed on 12 Mar 2020.
- xxxi. Rolf U. Halden. 2010. *Plastics and Health Risks*. *Annual Review of Public Health* 2010 31:1, 179-194. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.publhealth.012809.103714>

- xxxii. Ron C. (2017). *Asia's Booming Plastics Industry Prompts Ocean Pollution Fears*. Available at: <https://www.voanews.com/east-asia-pacific/asias-booming-plastics-industry-prompts-ocean-pollution-fears>. Viewed on 10 Apr 2020.
- xxxiii. Sally .H. (2019). *Landmark PET Report: Southeast Asia Plastic Crisis Result Of Government Inaction*. Available at: <https://www.greenqueen.com.hk/ga-circular-full-circle-pet-plastic-bottle-report-southeast-asia/>. Viewed on 10 Apr 2020
- xxxiv. Singh .J.(2019). *Waste Management Laws in India: Plastic & Biomedical Wastes Available at SSRN 3311161, 2019 – papers.ssrn.com*; <https://archive.nyu.edu/bitstream/2451/42242/2/Plastic%20Waste%20Management%20in%20India.pdf>
- xxxv. Steelys Drinkware. (2013). *The growing global landfill crisis*. Retrieved from <http://steelysdrinkware.com/growing-global-landfill-crisis/>.
- xxxvi. Sustainable Brands. (2017). *“2018 Circulars Nominate 43 Changemakers Paving the Path to a Circular Future.”* http://www.sustainablebrands.com/news_and_views/next_economy/sustainable_brands/2018_circulars_nominate_43_change_makers_paving_path_.
- xxxvii. Thu .N.A (2018) *Minimize plastic waste by changing consumer behavior*. Available at: <https://www.rmit.edu.vn/vi/tin-tuc/all-news/2018/mar/nguoi-tieu-dung-co-san-long-ung-ho-bao-bi-xanh>. Viewed on 14 Apr 2020
- xxxviii. Thuc .H .(2019). *Một số giải pháp chống rác thải nhựa tại Việt Nam*. Available at: <http://tapchimoitruong.vn/pages/article.aspx?item=Một-số-giải-pháp-chống-rác-thải-nhựa-tại-Việt-Nam-50534>. Viewed on 8 Mar 2020.
- xxxix. Thuy Van Pham Dan , An Truong Ha Phuong và Viet Nguyen Thanh. (2015). *Recycling polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and its applications*.
- xl. Vaughan, Adam. (2016). *“Biodegradable Plastic ‘False Solution’ for Ocean Waste Problem.”* *The Guardian*, May 23. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2016/may/23/biodegradable-plastic-false-solution-for-ocean-waste-problem>.
- xli. Vietnam Waste Management Department. (2019). *Management of plastic waste and nylon bags in Vietnam*. General Department of Environment.
- xl.ii. Woldemar d’Ambrières (2019). *Plastics recycling worldwide: current overview and desirable changes* », *Field Actions Science Reports [Online]*, Special Issue 19 | 2019, Online since 01 March 2019, connection on 07 March 2020. URL: <http://journals.openedition.org/factsreports/5102>
- xl.iii. <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2019/plastic-waste-circular-solution.aspx>
- xl.iiii. <https://www.eco-business.com/news/companies-solutions-to-global-plastic-crisis-miss-the-mark/>
- xl.v. <https://theintercept.com/2019/07/20/plastics-industry-plastic-recycling/>
- xl.vi. <https://www.shell.com/sustainability/environment/plastic-waste.html>